

Policy Brief

Restoring Pollinators in Europe: Evidence-Based Actions for Nature Restoration Plans

Buff-tailed bumblebee (*Bombus terrestris*) on
sweet cherry (*Prunus avium*) flower

The EU project *RestPoll*, in cooperation with other EU pollinator projects, summarised scientific evidence to inform actions related to the Nature Restoration Regulation.

Key messages

- Pollinators are essential for crop production, biodiversity, and ecosystem health. Pollinator conservation measures provide society-wide co-benefits, which include sustainable agriculture, soil and water health, and climate mitigation.
- Across Europe, pollinator habitats are degraded and insufficient. Expanding and enhancing high-quality habitats represents a critical opportunity to support pollinator populations.
- Evidence shows that the most effective measures for pollinator restoration are:
 1. Increasing the quality, quantity, and connectivity of flower-rich pollinator habitats (e.g. semi-natural grasslands, wildflower areas, hedgerows, flowering trees).
 2. Reducing the high intensity of land-use practices, including mowing, grazing, and pesticide use.
- Restoration measures are more effective when adapted to the local context and more likely to succeed when implemented in cooperation with farmers, researchers, and policymakers.

Policy recommendations

- **Restore and connect habitats** – Expand and link semi-natural grasslands, wildflower areas, hedgerows, and flowering trees to improve habitat quality, connectivity, and climate resilience.
- **Reduce high land-use intensity including chemical inputs** – Lower mowing and grazing intensity, minimise pesticide use, and adopt biodiversity-friendly farming practices.
- **Enable effective implementation** – Set context-specific objectives, engage stakeholders (farmers, ecologists, land managers, local authorities), provide financial and technical support, and establish robust monitoring systems to inform adaptive management and ensure sustainable, evidence-based restoration.

Red mason bee (*Osmia bicornis*) on mustard (*Sinapis alba*) flower

Context

Why pollinators matter:

Currently, many European landscapes are of low quality for pollinators, providing restoration opportunities through measures that focus on increasing their habitats and reducing land use intensity (Figure 1).

- **Societal co-benefits:** Pollinator conservation measures support sustainable agriculture, biodiversity, soil and water health, climate mitigation, and social benefits.
- **Regulatory Win-Wins:** Restoring pollinator populations (Article 10 NRR) can be achieved through the restoration of semi-natural grasslands (Article 4 NRR), and the inclusion of pollinator measures in urban green spaces (Article 8 NRR), agricultural (Article 11 NRR), and forest ecosystems (Article 12 NRR).

Pollinators are key indicators of ecosystem health, integrating the cumulative impacts of pressures such as land-cover change, habitat fragmentation, intensive land management, and pesticide use¹. In the context of the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), restoring habitats for pollinators serves both biodiversity goals and safeguards essential pollination services.

Evidence from across Europe shows marked declines in many pollinator groups²⁻⁵, underscoring the need for targeted habitat restoration, biodiversity-friendly farming practices⁶, and coherent monitoring systems⁷. Under Article 10 of the NRR, Member States are required to reverse pollinator declines by 2030 and increase populations thereafter through effective restoration actions. Article 11 reinforces this by mandating the restoration of agricultural ecosystems, with indicators such as the Butterfly Index used to track progress.

Consequently, to meet these multiple policy goals, Member States must implement restoration actions to maintain and enhance pollinator populations (Figure 1). These direct actions depend on enabling conditions (Tables 1-5).

Effective restoration measures

To effectively achieve Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) pollinator targets, implementing evidence-based restoration approaches are essential (Figure 1). There is a wide-ranging and complex evidence base on the effectiveness of different restoration measures. To support the implementation of Article 10 of the NRR in Europe, we brought together a cohesive overview, using an expert elicitation process involving 56 internationally recognised pollinator experts. Experts assessed various restoration actions and the enabling conditions required to maintain and restore pollinator populations. We identified two main categories of pollinator restoration action: **‘increase pollinator habitats’** and **‘reduce high land-use intensity’**.

Increase pollinator habitats

Reduce high land-use intensity

Expert opinion

Figure 1. Illustrates the expert consensus on key restoration measures that are grounded in the available scientific evidence and can be readily implemented to support pollinator restoration. The figure shows the effectiveness, ease of implementation, and cost for each measure as perceived by the respondents.

Recent research⁸ has revealed that for the main pollinator species groups, a simple relationship is true: the more semi-natural habitat, the more pollinators.

Pollinators need both more habitat and improvements in the quality of existing habitats in agricultural landscapes. The study demonstrated that when overall habitat area is low, increasing habitat quantity has the greatest impact. As habitat availability increases, improving its quality yields greater benefits than adding more habitat. The point at which this shift occurs differs among pollinator groups. Hoverflies reach it at a relatively low amount of habitat area, bees at an intermediate amount, and butterflies continue to benefit from additional habitat even at comparatively high habitat availability.

With a current target of 10% semi-natural habitat in agricultural landscapes, expanding habitat extent beyond this threshold appears necessary for bees and butterflies, requiring both restoration and the creation of additional pollinator-friendly habitat areas.

Increasing pollinator habitats at local and landscape scales can improve connectivity, while native seeds and plants help maintain genetic integrity and capacity for climate adaptation. Reducing land-use intensity in highly intensive landscapes, such as lowering pesticide inputs⁹ and decreasing mowing or grazing pressure¹⁰, further enhances habitat quality and allows diverse pollinator communities to recover.

Conservation measures are most effective when adapted to context (Figure 2).

Examples of successful restoration projects with stakeholder engagement at the

- Multi-country level - [BEESPOKE project](#)
- National level - [Ireland Pollinator Plan](#)
- Regional (urban) level - [More Bees for Berlin](#)
- Local level - [Rewilding Denmarkfield](#)

To ensure practical impact, interventions should be designed in consultation with key stakeholders. Ecologists, farmers, GIS specialists, land managers, and local authorities can help identify target species, suitable locations, feasible management practices, and maintenance requirements, increasing the likelihood that measures are appropriate, effective and sustainable.

Figure 2. Factors affecting success: socio-economic, management, landscape, and ecological.

Co-benefits of restoration measures

Pollinator restoration can be both ecologically effective and cost-effective, generating multi-functional landscapes that enhance pollinator populations while delivering wider benefits for biodiversity, soil and water health, sustainable agriculture, climate mitigation, and community well-being. It can also reduce the reliance on chemical inputs, supporting long-term environmental and economic resilience¹¹. Figure 3 gives an overview of this relationship.

Integrating pollinator habitat requirements into semi-natural grasslands (Article 4 NRR), urban green spaces (Article 8 NRR), agricultural systems (Article 11 NRR), and forest ecosystems (Article 12 NRR) offers a practical, efficient approach to implementation. These ecosystems provide strong foundations for pollinator recovery, delivering clear cross-sectoral win-wins under the Nature Restoration Regulation.

Common brimstone (*Gonepteryx rhamni*) on tuberosus pea (*Lathyrus tuberosus*) flower

Figure 3. Co-benefits of some example pollinator restoration actions. All three actions (wildflower areas, semi-natural grasslands, hedgerows) lead to higher plant species richness, provide habitats for pollinators and other animals, which can lead to increased pollination services and natural pest control. These restoration measures also benefit soil microbes and nutrient cycling, as well as promoting carbon storage in the soil, which prevents erosion, improves water infiltration, and mitigates climate change. Hedgerows provide shade and shelter for livestock, and they can be used as windbreaks to reduce crop damage. Hedgerows and semi-natural grasslands can provide forage for livestock, and establishing or maintaining them preserves traditional landscapes and cultural heritage. Establishing pollinator restoration actions creates opportunities for community engagement and education and improves landscape aesthetics.

Enabling conditions for effective action

Successful pollinator restoration relies on enabling conditions that promote behaviour change and support effective action. When developing their nature restoration plans, member states are encouraged to consider funding, stakeholder engagement, social acceptance, governance, technical capacity, and monitoring (Tables 1-5).

Tables 1–5. Key enabling conditions for pollinator restoration, summarising the expected impacts, practical guidance, and indicators across the domains of funding, stakeholder engagement, social acceptance, governance, technical capacity, and monitoring. Contributions from European Horizon projects are highlighted in yellow to illustrate how they support action areas.

ENABLING CONDITION: Financial incentives			
Action area	Expected impacts	Guidance	Indicators
Improve options for publicly funded incentives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Adoption of restoration; ↑ rural income stability 	Outcome-based payments; public subsidies; grants for establishment & long-term maintenance; investment in precision-agriculture & low-impact technologies; support for income diversification	Uptake of pollinator restoration actions
Improve options for privately-funded / market-based incentives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Adoption of restoration; ↑ market for biodiversity-friendly production; ↑ long-term economic resilience 	Encourage sustainable consumer choices; certification & labelling schemes; private-sector purchasing standards; corporate biodiversity commitments; market rewards for low-input & pollinator-friendly systems	Sales of pollinator-certified products; private-sector pollinator commitments; farmer participation in market-based schemes for pollinators
<p><i>VALOR</i> & <i>Butterfly</i> quantifies and models how pollinators support ecosystems, economies, and societies, and by giving stakeholders tools to assess and manage pollinator-related risks.</p>			

ENABLING CONDITION: Social acceptance			
Action area	Expected impacts	Guidance	Indicators
Integrate traditional & local knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Social acceptance; ↑ suitability of practices 	Co-design with communities; support knowledge exchange	Number of co-designed pollinator restoration projects

ENABLING CONDITION: Strong governance and institutional support			
Action area	Expected impacts	Guidance	Indicators
Monitoring and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Spending efficiency; ↑ ecological success; ↑ stakeholder clarity 	Define clear, measurable objectives; align with national biodiversity strategies	% targets met; pollinator species/habitat recovery rates
Prioritise at-risk species & habitats (e.g., Article 4, NRR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Conservation return; ↓ extinction risk; ↑ ecosystem stability 	Apply vulnerability scoring; prioritise funding	Area of critical pollinator habitat restored
Integrate pollinator restoration across sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Pollinator populations; ↑ citizen and stakeholder engagement 	Embed pollinator-friendly practices in urban and peri-urban planning, agricultural landscapes, and private lands	Number of participating stakeholders; area of pollinator habitat restored
Strengthen landscape connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Pollinator movement; ↑ pollinator populations 	Coordinate across jurisdictions; incentivise ecological corridors	Area of connected pollinator habitat
Integrate climate-smart design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Long-term resilience; ↓ replanting costs; ↑ soil health 	Climate-risk screening; adaptive genotypes; soil carbon restoration	Soil organic matter; pollinator/habitat survival rates
Support system-wide input reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Pollution; ↑ ecosystem health, human health; ↑ potential short-term yield risk 	Training, technical support, and financial assistance for reduced inputs, implement Target 18 of the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework	Reduction in pesticide use; yield stability metrics
Integrate under the ONE HEALTH framework	Human, animal & ecosystem health benefits	Harmonise environmental and agricultural policies; ensure regulatory capacity for enforcement & monitoring	—

EU PoMS monitoring approaches can be used to monitor the effectiveness of restoration actions and policies in different local landscapes and could be expanded to by including monitoring of pesticides or pollination services. [AGRI4POL](#) works with farmers and the agricultural sector to integrate pollinator-friendly practices into mainstream farming – not just as small conservation patches, but by redesigning farm landscapes, crop choices, and even breeding crops to benefit pollinators. Both [PollinERA](#) and [WildPosh](#) aim to make pesticide regulation and policy more protective across pollinator communities by improving how pesticide exposure and effects are understood and characterised.

ENABLING CONDITION: Technical capacity			
Action area	Expected impacts	Guidance	Indicators
Synthesised, actionable knowledge & tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Spending efficiency; ↑ ecological success; ↑ stakeholder clarity 	Provide integrated tools and evidence; align research and development to knowledge gaps	Uptake of pollinator restoration actions; area of pollinator habitat restored
<p>Conservation Evidence is the knowledge centre for restoration. It helps ensure that pollinator conservation is informed, effective, and scalable by consolidating what is proven to work, supporting evidence-based action (Fig. 1).</p> <p>RestPoll is developing a “Pollinator Restoration Toolbox” – a set of practical, transferable tools for stakeholders (farmers, governments).</p>			
Practice-centred knowledge & capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Practical adoption; ↑ trust in alternatives; ↑ empowerment 	Peer networks; independent advisory services; locally adapted grazing animals, seeds & plants; reduced management intensity; precision-farming support	Uptake of pollinator restoration actions; area of pollinator habitat restored
<p>RestPoll & Butterfly projects are using Living Labs to promote co-creation by farmers, scientists, NGOs, and stakeholders, integrating traditional and local knowledge to support biodiversity-friendly practices. ProPollSoil adds a critical dimension of soil health, as improving soil management improves the survival of ground-nesting pollinators.</p>			

ENABLING CONDITION: Monitoring			
Action area	Expected impacts	Guidance	Indicators
Implement adaptive management & monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Effectiveness; ↓ unintended consequences; ↓ wasted investment; ↑ transparency 	Integrate monitoring from the start; share open data	Pollinator monitoring; adaptive adjustments made
<p>STING project standardised pollinator diversity and population monitoring¹². Safeguard re-assesses pollinator statuses and models the drivers of decline.</p>			

Developed by the RestPoll project, this policy brief is grounded in an expert synthesis that included an online survey and workshops with researchers from Horizon projects and practitioners across Europe. Figure 1's results are based on an online survey of 56 experts from 20 European countries, spanning research, governmental, agricultural, and conservation sectors. Experts assessed a list of 17 measures and evaluated their perceived effectiveness, ease of implementation, and cost for each measure they were familiar with. This survey was complemented by a bespoke evidence synthesis conducted by Conservation Evidence, drawing on their recent butterfly and moth synopsis, with the most effective measures included in Figure 1. The enabling conditions shown in Tables 1-5 were identified through workshops with scientists and policy makers.

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Thick-legged hoverfly (*Syritta pipiens*) on mustard (*Sinapis alba*) flower